

1 **Our sixth sense: Humans locate the source**
2 **of ground vibrations with their feet.**

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17 eTOC blurb

18 Grimault et al.'s study reveals that humans possess a vibrotactile "sixth
19 sense". Standing individuals can locate the source of ground vibrations
20 using their feet, relying on timing and/or intensity differences between
21 them. This ability, analogous to binaural hearing, represents a previously
22 unknown channel for human spatial perception.

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24 Vision, hearing and olfaction are considered the primary sensory channels
25 for locating distant objects or living beings beyond our immediate reach¹.
26 While some animals also use ground-borne vibrations to sense their
27 environment, whether humans could exploit this channel to locate distant
28 vibration sources remained unexplored. Here, we show that humans
29 standing barefoot can pinpoint the source of mechanical waves
30 propagating through the ground. Our results suggest this ability relies on
31 comparing vibration intensity and arrival time between the two feet, a
32 process strikingly analogous to binaural sound localization by the auditory
33 system. Acting as a directional antenna, the feet provide a hitherto
34 overlooked sensory channel for accessing potentially vital spatial
35 information. This discovery not only reveals a hidden facet of human
36 perception but also raises important questions about the impact of
37 pervasive anthropogenic ground vibrations on how we navigate our
38 sensory world.

39 Locating the sources of sensory stimuli is a fundamental prerequisite
40 for animals, including humans, to interpret their environment and
41 respond appropriately. A variety of species are sensitive to vibrational
42 signals and may use them to communicate, escape predators or find
43 their prey^{2,3} (Figure 1A). Some species of invertebrates and snakes
44 have been shown to locate the source of ground vibration with great
45 accuracy (e.g., sand scorpion, Saharan sand vipers, sandfish lizard^{2,4}).
46 In mammals however, this localizing ability has been experimentally
47 demonstrated only in mole rats^{4,5}. While Humans readily perceive foot
48 vibrations⁶, this sensory channel is often considered functionally
49 limited, and it is unknown whether Humans can localize a distant
50 source of vibration. Yet, this ability could have been of primary
51 importance in the context of our ancestral hunter-gatherer's way of
52 life, where oriented displacements including anti-predatory behaviors
53 and foraging decisions depended on a mixture of sensory cues
54 provided by the environment.

55 In the present study, we tested human adults (N= 6 men and 6
56 women, aged 23-50 years) on their ability to report the direction of a
57 ground-borne vibration source under conditions that eliminated all
58 visual and auditory cues. During each trial (n = 80 / participant),
59 participants stood barefoot on a metal plate inside a semi-anechoic
60 booth, blindfolded and wearing a noise-cancelling headphone playing
61 low-pass filtered noise to mask any airborne sound (Figure 1B). A
62 vibratory device placed one meter away generated sinusoidal
63 vibrations at either 30 Hz or 125 Hz. These frequencies were chosen to
64 differentially activate cutaneous mechanoreceptors: 30 Hz stimulates
65 both fast-adapting (FA) and slow adapting (SA) receptors, whereas 125
66 Hz primarily activates FA receptors⁷. Vibrations were delivered from
67 one of four directions relative to the participant (0° = front, 180° =
68 back, + 90° = right, - 90° = left). To test our core hypothesis that
69 localization depends on comparing inputs between the feet,
70 participants performed the task while standing on either a single foot
71 or both feet. Stimulus order and conditions were counterbalanced
72 (Supplemental Information, Supplemental Table S2).

73 Our results provide the first direct evidence that humans can
74 determine the direction of ground-borne vibrations. As illustrated in
75 Figure 1C, performance was significantly above the 25% chance level
76 when participants used both feet to detect the 125 Hz stimulus,
77 reaching an average of 50% correct decisions (Bayesian Factor > 100,
78 indicating very strong evidence; Supplemental Table S1). Under this
79 optimal condition, accuracy was robust for sources located to the front
80 and sides, though we observed a notable increase in confusion for
81 sources originating from the back of participants (Figure 1D). This
82 pattern is a classic signature of spatial hearing that relies on binaural
83 cues. The dramatic improvement in performance when using two feet
84 compared to one strongly supports the hypothesis that the feet
85 function as a “vibrotactile antenna”, with the brain integrating
86 information from both to compute direction.

87 The computational mechanisms appear to be analogous to that of
88 auditory localization, which relies mainly on Interaural Time Difference
89 (delay of sound arrival between both ears) and Interaural Level
90 Difference (difference in sound amplitude). To investigate whether
91 analogous cues operate for vibrotactile localization via the feet, we
92 queried participants about their strategy. Eleven out of twelve reported
93 actively comparing sensations between their feet. This subjective
94 report aligns with the physical reality of the stimulus. Given the
95 average inter-feet distance of 26.4 ± 3.3 cm, we calculated the
96 estimated Inter-Feet Time Difference (IFTD) for a lateral source ($\pm 90^\circ$)
97 to be approximately 9 ms (See Supplemental Information). This
98 temporal delay is well within the discriminative capacity of the human
99 somatosensory system, which can resolve temporal differences on the
100 order of milliseconds^{7,8}. Furthermore, we measured Inter-Feet Level
101 Differences (IFLD, amplitude difference in terms of displacement) of 7
102 μm for the 30 Hz stimulus and 0.15 μm for the 125 Hz stimulus
103 (Supplemental Information). Considering the known sensitivity of
104 cutaneous mechanoreceptors⁹, these subtle amplitude differences
105 should also be perceptible. Since both IFTD and IFLD vary predictably
106 with source direction, they represent plausible and sufficient cues for
107 localization. The superior performance at 125 Hz likely stems from the
108 properties of FA receptors, whose rapid response characteristics are
109 ideally suited for encoding the precise onset timing and transient
110 amplitude information critical for resolving these subtle inter-feet
111 differences⁸.

112 In summary, this study demonstrates that humans possess a latent
113 “sixth sense”, a capacity to utilize vibrotactile perception through their
114 feet to gain spatial information about distant vibration sources. The
115 underlying sensory processing appears to share fundamental principles
116 with binaural hearing, suggesting that the comparison of signals from
117 paired sensors is a conserved, cross-modal strategy for spatial
118 computation in the brain. This discovery opens several exciting
119 avenues for future research. Neuroimaging studies could explore

120 whether vibrotactile localization recruits cortical areas that overlap
121 with those involved in auditory spatial processing. Further work could
122 also investigate whether this ability can be enhanced through training,
123 potentially offering new sensory substitution pathways for individuals
124 with visual impairments. Finally, our findings have profound
125 implications for understanding our interaction with modern
126 environments. We are constantly exposed to a cacophony of low-
127 frequency, ground-borne vibrations from traffic, machinery, and
128 infrastructure. This “vibrational noise pollution” may not only mask our
129 ability to perceive meaningful environmental signals but could also
130 have unsuspected, subliminal effects on our navigation, stress, and
131 cognitive load. Uncovering this dormant sensory skill is not just a
132 matter of scientific curiosity; it prompts a re-evaluation of our
133 relationship with the very ground beneath our feet.

134

135 **Supplemental information**

136 Supplemental information including experimental procedures, 2
137 Supplemental Tables, and supplemental references can be found with this
138 article online at XXX.

139

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178 **Declaration of Interests**

179 The authors declare no competing interests.

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185 **Figure 1. Humans can pinpoint the direction of a ground vibration**
186 **source.**

187 (A) Sensibility to substrate vibrations is known in various animals (blue
188 and red), but the ability to localize vibration source has been
189 experimentally confirmed in only a few (red). Human localization ability
190 was previously unexplored. (B) Experimental set-up. Blindfolded
191 participants, wearing noise-cancelling headphones, stood barefoot (one or
192 two feet) on a plate and reported the perceived direction (Front, 0°; Back,
193 180°; Left, -90°; Right, +90°) of a ground vibration source (1 m away; 30
194 Hz or 125 Hz sine waves; ~10 dB above detection threshold). (C)
195 Percentage of correct localization responses across conditions.
196 Performance significantly surpassed chance (25%, dashed red line), with
197 highest accuracy for two feet and 125 Hz stimulus. (D) Distribution of
198 reported directions under optimal conditions (two feet, 125 Hz) for each
199 source location (purple arrows). Dots indicate the mean number of trials
200 reported per direction (max 5); grey areas represent SD across
201 participants. Responses generally aligned with the true source direction,
202 except for back condition.

203 **SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION**

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	BF ₊₀	error %
all conditions	492.946	NaN
30 Hz & 1 foot	2.698	1.910×10 ⁻⁵
30 Hz & 2 feet	0.723	4.915×10 ⁻⁶
125 Hz & 1 foot	0.382	0.032
125 Hz & 2 feet	242.675	NaN

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207 **Supplemental Table S1. Effect of experimental conditions on**
208 **localization accuracy.** Results of Bayesian one sample t-test assessing
209 whether accuracy in each condition exceeded the 25% chance level (H1).
210 Bayesian factors and associated errors are shown. BFs > 10 = strong
211 support for H1 ; > 3 = moderate support for H1 ; < 0.3 = moderate
212 support for H0 ; < 0.1 = strong support for H0.

213

	position of the accelerometer	frequency	acceleration (m.s ⁻²)	displacement pic to pic (mm)	dB SL
Intensity during experiment	right foot (closest to the stim)	30 Hz	0.63	0.01783	10
		125 Hz	0.18	0.00029	10
	left foot	30 Hz	0.38	0.01078	10
		125 Hz	0.09	0.00014	10
Intensity at detection threshold	right foot (closest to the stim)	30 Hz	0.20	0.00564	0
		125 Hz	0.05	0.00008	0
	left foot	30 Hz	0.12	0.00341	0
		125 Hz	0.02	0.00004	0

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Supplemental Table S2. Detection thresholds and intensity levels used for the experiments.

219 **SUPPLEMENTAL EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES**

220 **Participants.**

221 Twelve participants (6 men and 6 women, aged 23 to 50 years) were
222 recruited for the study. All participants signed informed consent prior to
223 participation. The study was performed under the authorization
224 IRBN692019/CHUSTE.

225

226 **Experimental set up.**

227 Experiments were conducted within a semi-anechoic booth (4.6 m X 3.45
228 m) designed to minimize external auditory and vibrational noise. The
229 booth floor consisted of a 3 mm thick iron plate supported by anti-
230 vibration cones. Two vibrating pots (PCB SmartShaker K2004E01) served
231 as vibration sources; They were positioned 1 meter from the designated
232 participant location (center of the plate), with an angle between of 135
233 degrees. Each vibrating pot was suspended from the booth ceiling and
234 rigidly coupled to the floor to ensure efficient vibration transmission into
235 the floor.

236

237 **Stimuli.**

238 Stimuli were sinusoidal vibrations at 30 Hz or 125 Hz. These frequencies
239 were chosen based on prior research^{S1} indicating that 30 Hz ground-borne
240 vibrations activate both Fast Adapting: (FAI, FAII) and Slow Adapting (SAI,
241 SAII) cutaneous mechanoreceptors, while 125 Hz vibrations primarily
242 stimulate FA receptors. Stimulus amplitude was set 10 dB above the
243 average detection threshold, determined in a pilot study using a simple
244 up-down adaptive procedure (consistent with thresholds reported in ^{S2, S3};
245 see Supplementary Table S2 for absolute levels). Vibration amplitude was
246 calibrated and equalized between the two potential source locations using
247 an accelerometer (PCB Shear accelerometer 333B32) connected to an
248 acquisition card (ROGA instrument), with measurements taken at the
249 participant's central standing location.

250 The vibrating pots produced an audible airborne sound (62 dB SPL at 1.5
251 m height, center point; measured with Bruel & Kjaer 2250 class A
252 sonometer, 1-octave frequency analysis). To mask this sound and preclude
253 auditory localization cues, participants wore disposable ear-plugs
254 underneath active noise-canceling headphones (Shure AONIC50) playing
255 continuous low-pass filtered pink noise (cutoff 500 Hz, -48 dB/octave
256 slope) at 87 dB SPL. Visual cues were eliminated by conducting the
257 experiment in complete darkness and having participants wear a
258 disposable sleep mask. Participants were naïve to the room configuration
259 and the number or location of vibrating sources.

260

261 **Experimental procedure.**

262 Participants stood barefoot at the designated center point of the iron
263 plate, wearing thin disposable fabric overshoes for hygiene. A handle
264 suspended from the ceiling was provided for stability. Before each trial,
265 participants were instructed whether to stand on one foot (left or right,
266 counterbalanced across trials) or both feet. On each trial, a vibration
267 stimulus was presented from one of four directions relative to the
268 participant's facing direction (Front: 0°, Back: 180°, Left: -90°; Right:
269 +90°). Following stimulus presentation, participants verbally reported the
270 perceived direction using a four-alternative forced-choice procedure
271 ('Front', 'Back', 'Left', or 'Right'). The presentation order of conditions
272 (vibration frequency: 30/125 Hz; stance: one/two feet; source direction:
273 Front/Back/Left/Right) was pseudo-randomized and counterbalanced
274 across participants. Each participant completed 5 repetitions for each
275 unique combinations of conditions, resulting in 80 trials total. The
276 experiment lasted approximately one hour per participant, including a
277 short break.

278

279 **Statistical analysis.**

280 Localization accuracy (percent correct, p) was transformed using the logit
281 function $\text{logit}(p) = \ln\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right)$ prior to analysis. To determine if
282 performance significantly exceeded the chance level (25%), Bayesian one
283 sample t-tests were performed on the logit transformed data for each
284 condition, with default Cauchy prior. Bayes Factors (BF_{10}) were calculated
285 to quantify the evidence favoring the alternative hypothesis (H_1 : accuracy
286 $> 25\%$) over the null hypothesis (H_0 : accuracy $\leq 25\%$). We interpreted
287 $BF_{10} > 10$ as strong evidence for H_1 , $BF_{10} > 3$ as moderate evidence for
288 H_1 , $BF_{10} < 0.3$ as moderate evidence for H_0 , and $BF_{10} < 0.1$ as strong
289 evidence for H_0 .

290

291 **Authors contributions**

292 The original idea for this research was conceived by NG. NG, EK and FP
293 participated in the experiments and the analysis of results. All authors
294 participated in the writing.

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297 **Supplemental References**

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